

Interaction of Rare Earth Metal Ions with Phenylacetohydroxamic Acid

M. JANARDHAN RAO*, B. SETHURAM and T. NAVANEETH RAO

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 29 February 1983, revised 5 May 1986, accepted 7 June 1986

Metal-ligand stability constant of binary complexes of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III} with 2-phenylacetohydroxamic acid have been determined potentiometrically at different temperatures and at a constant ionic strength. Trends in the values of successive stability constants are discussed. Both enthalpy and entropy factors favour complex formation.

METAL complexes of hydroxamic acids are known as good fungicides¹ and herbicides²; hydroxamic acids and their salts have also been used extensively in the preservation of food³. Hydroxamic acids are known to possess antitubercular activity⁴, to effect photostabilisation of polymers⁵ and to inhibit the decomposition of urea to NH₃.

The rare earth ions exhibit a maximum coordination number larger than the six; and in order to obtain a clear understanding of the factors which influence the formation and stability of the rare earth chelates, it was thought worthwhile to study binary complex formation of phenylacetohydroxamic acid with some rare earth metal ions, such as La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III}.

Experimental

Metal nitrate solutions were prepared and standardised by standard methods⁷⁻⁹. All the chemicals were of AnalaR quality. Phenylacetohydroxamic acid was prepared by the known method¹⁰ and recrystallised from dilute acetic acid and repeatedly washed with petroleum ether. Double-distilled and CO₂-free water was employed for preparing the solutions.

A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter in conjunction with glass and calomel electrodes was used for the measurement of pH. The pH meter was calibrated using the standard buffers having pH 4.00, 7.00 and 9.18. The experimental procedure for the determination of stability constants of the binary complexes consisted of pH-metric titration of PAHA solution containing the rare earth M(III) ions in 5 : 1, 10 : 1 and 20 : 1 ratios by sodium hydroxide. Ionic strength was maintained constant (0.1 M) by adding potassium nitrate solution. Experiments were conducted at 20, 30, 40, 50 ± 0.1°.

pH titration curves for La^{III}-PAHA system at $\mu=0.1$ and 30° are given in Fig. 1. Analysis of

titration curves (I, II and III) reveals that metal ion hydrolysis in the presence of PAHA occurs at higher pH. By measuring horizontal distances between curves I and II, II and III (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_a$ and $\bar{n}$ values were calculated using the expressions given

Fig. 1. pH titration curves of acidified PAHA in the presence and absence of La^{III} at 30° and 0.100 ionic strength. (I) HNO₃ (2.00 × 10⁻³ M), (II) HNO₃ (2.00 × 10⁻³ M) + PAHA (1.00 × 10⁻³ M), (IIIa) HNO₃ (2.00 × 10⁻³ M) + PAHA (1.00 × 10⁻³ M) + La^{III} (2.00 × 10⁻⁴ M), (IIIb) HNO₃ (2.00 × 10⁻³ M) + PAHA (2.00 × 10⁻³ M) + La^{III} (2.00 × 10⁻⁴ M), and (IIIc) HNO₃ (2.00 × 10⁻³ M) + PAHA (2.00 × 10⁻³ M) + La^{III} (1.00 × 10⁻⁴ M).

* Present address * Department of Chemistry, University College of Engineering, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007.

by Irving and Rossotti^{11,12}. The successive formation constants K_1 , K_2 and K_3 were evaluated by graphical method¹².

Results and Discussion

Metal—ligand stability constants were calculated at constant ionic strength (0.1M) and at different temperatures (20, 30, 40 and 50°). In general, the stability order, $K_1 > K_2 > K_3$, were observed for all the metal ions (Table 1), though the difference in the values between the three constants are not that

much indicating that there is almost equal tendency for the formation of the successive complexes. The order of the log K ($K=1, 2, 3$) values for the metal ions was found to be $\text{La}^{\text{III}} < \text{Ce}^{\text{III}} < \text{Pr}^{\text{III}} < \text{Nd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Gd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Sm}^{\text{III}} < \text{Dy}^{\text{III}}$. The ΔG and ΔH values also follow the same order. In most of the rare earth chelates, when $e^{\Delta S}/r$ is plotted against log K values, a linear plot is obtained with break at Gd, which is commonly known as gadolinium break¹³. The same trend was observed in the present study also. For all the systems, the negative ΔH and positive ΔS values obtained indicated that both enthalpy and entropy factors favour complex formation.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY RARE EARTH COMPLEXES OF PAHA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (°C)

$\mu=0.10$					
Metal ion (III)	Stability constant	20°	30°	40°	50°
La	log K_1	5.45	5.39	5.32	5.25
	log K_2	4.90	4.85	4.80	4.73
	log K_3	4.39	4.35	4.27	4.21
Ce	log K_1	5.62	5.54	5.48	5.43
	log K_2	5.23	5.16	5.09	5.02
	log K_3	4.48	4.40	4.31	4.25
Pr	log K_1	5.67	5.59	5.52	5.49
	log K_2	5.37	5.30	5.22	5.16
	log K_3	4.52	4.45	4.38	4.36
Nd	log K_1	5.75	5.69	5.62	5.57
	log K_2	5.41	5.35	5.29	5.21
	log K_3	4.55	4.50	4.42	4.36
Sm	log K_1	6.05	5.99	5.92	5.85
	log K_2	5.72	5.65	5.57	5.52
	log K_3	4.88	4.80	4.73	4.67
Gd	log K_1	5.98	5.94	5.88	5.82
	log K_2	5.67	5.62	5.56	5.50
	log K_3	4.71	4.65	4.60	4.52
Dy	log K_1	6.32	6.25	6.18	6.13
	log K_2	5.88	5.80	5.72	5.67
	log K_3	5.04	4.95	4.89	4.83

References

1. H. JUNICHI, K. KYOICHI, K. NOBUE and S. KIYONORI, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1971, 19, 369.
2. Y. ABE and O. C. DIAGAKU, *Igaku Zasshi*, 1960, 9, 4039 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 61, 9977).
3. J. J. BERRABOOM, US Pat. 446 630/1969 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 71, 37601).
4. T. URBANKI and C. BELZECKI, *Gruslica*, 1954, 22, 681.
5. M. JANARDHAN RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. NAVANEETH RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 516.
6. S. J. WORTHAM, US Pat. 3 843 701/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 82, 77115).
7. M. JANARDHAN RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. NAVANEETH RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 1136.
8. M. JANARDHAN RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. NAVANEETH RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 379.
9. M. JANARDHAN RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. NAVANEETH RAO, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1982, 91, 111.
10. W. B. RENFROW and C. R. HOUSER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2308.
11. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
12. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
13. T. MOELLER, L. C. THOMPSON and R. ERRUS in "Rare Earth Research", ed. E. N. ERLBER, MacMillan, New York, 1963, p. 3.